

Polarographic Study of Photoisomerisation of *o*-Nitrobenzaldehyde

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Kinetics of the photochemical reaction of *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde has been studied polarographically in the range of 4360 to 3130 Å. The aldehyde is reduced at the dropping Hg electrode and *C-V* curve with well-defined diffusion range is obtained.

Photoisomeric change of *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde to *o*-nitrosobenzoic acid under the influence of light in the range 4360 to 3130 Å has been observed by Leighton and Lucy (*J. Chem. Phys.*, 1934, **6**, 498). The present investigation is undertaken to study the kinetics of this photochemical reaction polarographically. *o*-Nitrobenzaldehyde is found to be reduced at the dropping mercury electrode and current-voltage (*C-V*) curve with well-defined diffusion range is obtained. Diffusion current is found to be proportional to the concentration of *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde. Influence of sunlight on *C-V* curve of *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde is observed due to isomeric change of the same. The decrease of wave height of *C-V* curve of *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde under the influence of light has been interpreted and applied in the study of the reaction kinetics of photoisomeric change of the same.

EXPERIMENTAL

All measurements were made against saturated calomel electrode. The solution was deoxygenated by passing hydrogen through the solution. Same jet tube was used for dropping mercury electrode throughout the experiment.

Drop time of mercury was adjusted to 4-5 seconds per drop. All the chemicals used were analytical reagent (AnalaR). *o*-Nitrobenzaldehyde was purified by the method adopted by Leighton and Lucy (*loc. cit.*).

A known volume of a solution of 25% acetone in 0.01*N*-HCl—0.1*N*-KCl was electrolysed. An increasing potentials in the range of 0 to 1.33 volts (vs. S.C.E.) were applied to the cell and corresponding currents were noted. Current was plotted against the corresponding applied voltage (vs. S.C.E.) and *C-V* curve was obtained. To the same solution various amounts of 4.0×10^{-3} *M* *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde solution were added from a calibrated burette and polarograms were taken for different concentrations of *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde. Diffusion current at each concentration of *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde was determined from *C-V* curve, subtracting the current for blank. The electrolysis vessel was kept covered with a black paper during the measurements of current-voltage. It should be noted that the reduction potentials of acetone and aldehyde (Adkins and Cox, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, **60**, 1151) group of *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde are beyond the range of potential applied. Moreover, no photochemical decomposition of acetone could be detected polarographically within the above range of applied voltage.

To study the reaction kinetics of photoisomerisation of *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde, the following procedure was adopted.

A polarogram of *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde ($4.5 \times 10^{-4} M$) in 25% acetone, 0.01*N*-HCl, and 0.1 *N*-KCl was taken initially. It was then exposed to direct sunlight with constant stirring for definite intervals of time, namely, 10, 21, 30, 60, and 120 minutes and polarograms were taken after each exposure. Wave height was found to decrease successively at each exposure initially, but it remained unchanged in the later stages when the entire amount of *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde was converted into *o*-nitrosobenzoic acid. Diffusion current from each polarogram was measured from the wave height, subtracting the current from blank.

TABLE I

Relation of diffusion current to the conc. of *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde in 25% acetone, 0.01 *N*-HCl, and 0.1*N*-KCl.

At 0.6 volt (vs. S.C.E.). Galv. sensitivity = 4.3×10^{-8} amp./mm.

Conc. ($c \times 10^4 M$)	1.00	1.95	2.86	3.72	4.55
Diffusion current (deflection in cm).	2.3	4.7	6.7	8.7	10.7

DISCUSSION

As the concentration of the aldehyde was increased, the wave height also increased (Fig. 1). Table I shows that the concentration bears a linear relation with diffusion current

FIG. 1. Polarograms for *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde in 25% acetone + 0.01*N*-HCl + 0.1*N*-KCl.
 c = conc. of the aldehyde.

of *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde according to the Ilkovic equation (*Coll. Czech. Chem. Comm.*, 1934, **6**, 498). The decrease of wave height, *i.e.*, the diffusion current of *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde on exposure to light, is due to isomeric change of the same to *o*-nitrosobenzoic acid (*cf.* Fig. 2). Theoretically a linear relation should hold between the decrease of diffusion current and the amount of *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde isomerised by light. This enables us to study the kinetics of the photochemical reaction. The value of specific reaction rate (*k*) for first order reaction was calculated (*cf.* Table II).

TABLE II

Kinetics of photoisomerisation of o-nitrobenzaldehyde in 25% acetone, 0.01N-HCl and 0.1N-KCl.

Initial conc. of *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde = $4.5 \times 10^{-4}M$. Temp. = 30°. $a = i_{d_0} - i_{d_\infty} = 43$.

Time. (t)	Diffusion current (<i>i_d</i>) Galv. deflection.	$a - x = i_{d_0} - i_{d_t}$	Log (a - x).	$k = \frac{2.303}{t} \log \frac{a}{a-x}$
0 min.	103 mm			
10	81	21	1.3222	0.07168
21	70	10	1.0000	0.06900
30	65	5	0.7404	0.06860
60	60	..	..	..
∞	60	..	..	..

FIG. 2. Influence of sunlight on *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde. E_T = Time for exposure to light.

According to Leighton and Lucy (*loc. cit.*) this photochemical reaction of *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde to *o*-nitrosobenzoic acid proceeds entirely by an intramolecular rearrangement with no side or reverse reaction. The course of electrolytic reduction of aromatic mononitro compounds was investigated by Haber (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1900, **32**, 271).

Employing nitrobenzene as an example, the main stages of the reduction in alkaline and acid solutions are: nitrobenzene $\rightarrow$ nitrosobenzene $\rightarrow$ phenylhydroxylamine $\rightarrow$ aniline. The final stage of reaction therefore would be

The reduction of nitrosobenzene to aniline is represented as:

On the same line it may be assumed that electrolytic reduction of nitro group of *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde is as:

and that of photoisomerised *o*-nitrosobenzoic acid is

It is clear from equations (3) and (4) that nitro group of *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde in order to be reduced to amino group requires 6 hydrogen atoms, whereas nitroso group requires 4 hydrogen atoms. In the process of electro-reduction, the current detected is due to discharge of ions (here hydrogen ions). So diffusion current of *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde should decrease on irradiating the substance since concentration of *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde (in reduction 6H^+ involved) decreases due to conversion to *o*-nitrosobenzoic acid (in reduction 4H^+ involved). When the conversion is complete, there should be no further decrease of diffusion current as it will be then given solely by the reduction of *o*-nitrosobenzoic acid. It appears from Fig. 2 that the half-wave potentials of the both isomeric forms are very near to each other. The decrease of diffusion current should be proportional to the amount of *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde isomerised by light. The proposed mechanism has been justified by the determination of specific reaction rate, *k*, of photoisomerisation of *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde (cf. Table II). The value is fairly constant on the consideration of probable slight variation of intensity of sunlight during the whole operation.

The present investigation further reveals that polarographic method of analysis with a suitable electro-reducible substance may be employed to determine the total quantity of light that causes a photochemical reaction. Hence a polarograph may be used as an actinometer.

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